

ELECTRICAL RESISTIVITY MEASUREMENT:
A TECHNIQUE TO MONITOR DAMAGE PROGRESSION IN
CFRP-LAMINATES

K. Schulte
(DFVLR, Institut für Werkstoff-Forschung, 5000 Köln 90,
W.-Germany)

Ch. Baron
(Hüls AG, 4370 Marl, W.-Germany)

ABSTRACT

The variation of the mechanical stiffness during fatigue loading has been proven to be an important qualitative and quantitative damage analogue. A correlation between stiffness reduction and the development of the various types of damage, as transverse and longitudinal intraply cracking or delamination growth, has been made. However, the in-situ recording of fibre fracture occurring during static or fatigue loading in cfrp-laminates has not yet been made. The measurement of the variation of the electrical resistivity during loading promises to be a valuable technique for this purpose. In the case of a usual metal sample the conductivity is essentially the same for any direction of current flow through the sample. In cfrp samples the conductivity is not homogeneous and depends on the orientation and on the conductivity of the carbon fibres. Its change can therefore be related to fibre fracture. The resistivity varies with temperature. It is therefore necessary to correlate the resistivity with the temperature observed during a fatigue test. The resistivity of cfrp-laminates is further dependent on the applied load, the fibre volume fraction, the laminate stacking sequence and the fibre type. Knowing all these factors, it is possible to correlate the change in the electrical resistivity to damage and failure of the load bearing 0°-fibres.

INTRODUCTION

The various damage mechanisms in cfrp-laminates occurring under static and fatigue loading have been described in [1-3]. Special attention has been given to describe failure of the load bearing 0°-fibres as their rupture initiates specimen failure. However, detecting fibre fracture seems only to be possible by indirect measurements, e.g. stiffness reduction during loading, or directly using destructive testing techniques.

Carbon fibres are electrically conductive. It seems to be therefore advantageous to take the variation of the electrical conductivity, respectively the increase in the electrical resistance, as an indicator for rupture of fibres in a cfrp-laminate.

In case of metallic materials their conductivity is by far independent of the direction of current flow within a specimen. However, in cfrp-laminates the conductivity is not homogenous but mainly depends on the fibre orientation. The specific resistance of carbon fibres ($1500 \cdot 10^{-8} \Omega\text{m}$) is essentially higher as in metals (e.i. aluminium $2,5 \cdot 10^{-8} \Omega\text{m}$). The epoxy matrix with its high electrical resistivity ($\approx 10^{21} \cdot 10^{-8} \Omega\text{m}$) can be taken as an insulator. Fibre fracture in a composite with continuous fibres will therefore lead to a sudden and stepwise increase in the electrical resistance. The method itself is in general similar to the potential drop technique used in metals to detect crack propagation [4]. In a cfrp-laminate the electrical resistance is mainly dependent on the volume fraction and length of the C-fibres and the laminate stacking sequence.

In carbon fibres the electrical resistivity decreases with increasing temperature [5]. Under fatigue loading an increase in the laminate temperature is observed, dependent on frequency, load level and laminate stacking sequence [6]. Under fatigue loading it is therefore necessary to detect the temperature variation and correlate it with changes in resistivity. If this is taken into consideration then the variation of the electrical conductivity can be taken as a measure to detect fracture of load bearing 0°-fibres, which was first published in [7] for static tensile testing and tension-tension fatigue and in [8] for three point bend testing.

EXPERIMENTAL

In Fig. 1 is schematically shown the set up for the detection of the electrical resistivity. A constant electric current of about 50 mA is introduced into the specimen end surface of a cfrp test piece. The value of 50 mA was arbitrarily chosen, as it was the lowest constant current that could be fixed at the current source available. However, an increase in specimen temperature due to this relatively high electric current could not be found, only when the current flow exceeded 1 A. The voltage, dependent on the current flow of 50 mA, was detected with an accuracy of about 0,01 mV. With the aid of a reverse voltage source the total voltage, was suppressed to about zero. The variation in voltage due to loading of the specimen could now directly be plotted. The Ohm's-law ($R = U/I$; $R = \text{Resistivity}$, $U = \text{Voltage}$, $I = \text{Current}$) allowed to transfer the voltage into a resistivity value.

End tabs of glasfibre reinforced plastics were used to insulate the specimen against the grips and for load transfer. The electric current was introduced into the specimen with the aid of a copper plate which surpassed the specimen ends (Fig. 2). The electrical contact between carbon fibres and the copper plate was made with a liquid silver solution which covered the carbon fibre ends and the copper plate as well. To increase the contact between the C-fibres and the silver the specimen ends were polished with a 3 μm aluminium oxide powder. After polishing, the C-fibres which are harder than the epoxy resin, are sticking out of the matrix and allow a better current transfer. The measurement cables are soldered against the copper plate.

The dependence of the electrical resistivity due to fibre loading was measured on a screw driven tensile test machine with a constant stroke of 1mm/min. The fatigue tests were performed on a servohydraulic test machine.

In addition to the electrical resistivity also the specimen temperature was detected with a thermocouple (Fe-Ni). To avoid a heat flux from the test machine (actuator) into the specimen the grips were cooled to a constant temperature of about 22°C. Two extensometers were applied to either side of the specimen to continuously measure the specimen strain in each load cycle. The variation of the strain rate (in a load controlled test) can directly be used to derive the variation of the secant modulus of the specimen. This can be taken as a damage analogue and is often referred to as "stiffness" reduction [1,2]. The temperature increase measured due to fatigue loading can as well be correlated to damage development [6]. The fatigue tests were performed in tension-tension under a constant R'-value of $R' = 0,1$ ($R' = \sigma_u / \sigma_o$; σ_u = minimum and σ_o = maximum stress in a load cycle) at a frequency of 10 Hz.

The cfrp test specimen had a width of 25 mm and a length of 190 mm. The thickness was dependent on the laminate stacking sequence, with about 1 mm for the unidirectional laminate $[0_8]$ and 2 mm for the cross-ply laminate $[0_2, 90_2, 0_2, 90_2]_s$.

HTA carbon fibres from the Toho-Beslon company were used with an epoxy matrix system (MY 720) from the Ciba-Geigy company.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TESTS UNDER STATIC LOADING

Fracture of single carbon fibres can already be expected in cfrp-laminates under static loading [3]. The manifestation of fibre fracture is in general not possible during a load test, with the exception, fibres split off the specimen surface and can be observed by the naked eye. However, the variation in electrical resistivity during static loading is a clear indicator of fibre fracture. This is shown in Fig. 3. In addition to the stress-strain curve of an unidirectional specimen $[0_8]$, the variation of the electrical resistivity is plotted versus the laminate strain. The electrical resistivity increases first about linearly with increasing fibre strain. This increase in the electrical resistivity R has to be expected, because

$$R = \frac{\rho \cdot l}{A}$$

with ρ = specific electrical resistivity, l = length of electrical current and A = cross section of electric current; l increases under load and A decreases. After about 0.7 % strain the electrical resistivity varies not linearly, which can be related to fibre fracture. Above 1.2 % strain the electrical resistivity stepwise jumps to higher values. This can directly be related to fibre fracture. The fibre fracture is partly indicated - but with a much lower resolution - in the stress-strain curve.

TESTS UNDER FATIGUE LOADING

If cfrp-laminates are cyclically loaded, a number of various damage mechanisms can be observed [1,2]. Fibre fracture can comparatively early be observed. It was shown in previous studies, that the variation of the specimen stiffness can be taken as an indicator (analogue) which is highly sensitive to damage especially fibre fracture. However, a selection of the various damage mechanisms occurring is not possible with this method.

The variation of the specimen temperature can be taken as an analogue to detect damage in a composite specimen. Increasing specimen temperature is a result of increasing matrix damage. A good correlation between increase in specimen temperature and stiffness reduction was found [6].

In Fig. 4 is shown the result of a fatigue test on a $[0_2, 90_2, 0_2, 90_2]$ cross-ply laminate. Specimen temperature, electrical resistivity and stiffness reduction were continuously measured. The typical stiffness reduction and temperature curves for a cross-ply laminate were found. The electrical resistivity increases just from the beginning of the fatigue test, what can be related either to the overall loading of the specimen (mean load) but also to 0° fibre fracture, initiated in the 0° -ply at that locations, where transverse cracks in the 90° -plies touch against the 0° -ply. During the course of further fatigue loading the electrical resistivity decreases due to the increasing specimen temperature. Near the end of fatigue life again the electrical resistivity increases and the stiffness decreases, both stepwise. It was shown in previous papers [1,2] that the final reduction in stiffness can be related to single fibre failure or even bundles of fibres.

The method of monitoring the electrical resistivity is an appropriate nondestructive in situ technique to investigate fibre fracture.

Fig. 4 also shows a temperature increase during the entire fatigue life. Due to the temperature increase the electrical resistivity of the specimen decreases. Only with the formation of fibre fracture an erratic increase in electrical resistivity occurs. The observed decrease in the electrical resistivity can lead to misinterpretations. A correction of the electrical resistivity on the basis of temperature measurements is therefore necessary. The variation of the electrical resistivity due to the temperature of a cross-ply test piece has to be identified (Fig. 10). From this curve the equivalent resistivity values can be taken to correct the data of the fatigue test. The corrected values for the electrical resistivity are shown in Fig. 6. A continuous increase or at least a constance in the electrical resistivity can be observed, but no more a decrease.

CONCLUSION

- The measurement of the electrical resistivity can be used to in-situ detect damage in a carbon/epoxy specimen or part.
- Dependent on the load, applied to a carbon/epoxy part or specimen, the electrical resistivity varies due to the actual strain.
- The conclusion to be drawn is: The measurement of the electrical resistivity in a cfrp-part is a nondestructive evaluation technique (NDE) with which composite parts can be inspected even when they are in use.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank Dipl.-Ing. V. Bachmann and cand.-ing. M. Dusy for valuable discussions and performing some of the tests. The support by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- [1] R.D. Jamison, K. Schulte, K.L. Reifsnider, W.W. Stinchcomb
ASTM-STP 836 (1984) pp. 21-55.
- [2] K. Schulte
Proceedings, European Symposium on "Damage Development and
Failure Processes, Composite Materials" Leuven (Belgium),
4.-6. May 1987, pp. 39-54.
- [3] K. Schulte
Proceedings "Advancing with Composites". International
Conference on Composite Materials, 10.-12. May 1988, Milano
(Italy), pp. 105-113.
- [4] V. Bachmann, K.H. Trautmann, P. Sengebusch, R. Marissen
Proc. DVM-AK "Betriebsfestigkeit", München, 7.-8. February 1984,
pp. 239-263.
- [5] L.A. Scruggs, W.J. Gajda, jr.
IEEE EMC Symposium, Seattle, WA, USA, 2.-4. August 1977,
pp. 396-402.
- [6] H. Neubert, H. Harig, K. Schulte
ICCM-VI/ECCM-2, London, 20-24 July 1987, Vol. 1, pp. 1.359-
1.368.
- [7] Ch. Baron, K. Schulte
Z. Materialprüfung (1988).
- [8] D.A. Robinson
U.S.N.A. - Trident Scholar project report, No. 148 (1987).

Fig. 1 Schematic of the test configuration for monitoring the electrical resistivity, the specimen temperature and the strain of cfrp-specimen.

Fig. 2 Introduction of the electrical current into the specimen end surface of a cfrp-specimen, schematically.

Fig. 3 Tensile test. Stress strain curve and dependent electrical resistivity of a cfrp-specimen. Unidirectional laminate.

Fig. 4 Variation of secant modulus, temperature and electrical resistivity during cyclic loading (% of fatigue life) of a cross-ply laminate.

Fig. 5 Variation of the electrical resistivity due to temperature change. Unloaded specimen. Curve used for the correction of the temperature dependent electrical resistivity in Fig. 9.

Fig. 6 Variation of temperature and electrical resistivity during cycling loading (% of fatigue life). Electrical resistivity corrected due to temperature variation.